

TEACHERS' INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE, MANAGEMENT SUPPORT, AND SCHOOL INFRASTRUCTURE: BASES FOR INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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Teachers' Instructional Competence, Management Support, and School Infrastructure: Bases for Intervention Program

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Abstract

The effectiveness of physical education program to students' holistic development is profoundly influenced by teachers' instructional competence, management support, and school infrastructure. This descriptive-correlational research aimed to determine the teachers' instructional competence, management support and school infrastructure in the Schools Division of Iloilo, Province of Iloilo, Philippines for the School Year 2022-2023 as evaluated by the MAPEH teachers when they were classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, length of service and position. Frequency count, percentage, rank and mean, T-Test, Analysis of Variance, and Pearson r were used to compute the data gathered. The findings of the study revealed that majority of the respondents were 40 years old and below, bachelor's degree, medium length of service, and teacher I-III. Majority of the respondents are with "Very High" instructional competence, management support, and school infrastructure. Further, no significant differences in teachers' instructional competence existed when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, length of service and position; management support existed when classified according to age, educational attainment length of service, and position, and teachers' school infrastructure existed when classified according to age, educational attainment length of service, and position. However, there is a significant relationship existed among teachers' instructional competence, management support; management support and school infrastructure, and management support and school infrastructure.

Keywords: *instructional competence, management support, school infrastructure*

Introduction

The educational landscape has increasingly recognized the significance of comprehensive physical education in fostering holistic student development. In the Schools Division of Iloilo, the integration of the K to 12 Curriculum underscores this by prioritizing physical education to enhance students' physical, mental, and emotional well-being. However, the effectiveness of physical education programs is profoundly influenced by teachers' instructional competence, management support, and school infrastructure. Teachers' expertise in delivering engaging and effective physical education curricula is crucial for student learning and performance. Additionally, management support plays a pivotal role in providing resources, professional development, and a conducive environment for teachers to thrive. Concurrently, adequate school infrastructure, including proper facilities and equipment, is essential for the practical application of physical education activities. Despite the acknowledged importance of these factors, there is a notable gap in research examining their collective impact on learners' academic performance in physical education. This study seeks to bridge this gap by investigating how these determinants interact to influence academic outcomes, aiming to provide actionable insights for policy and curriculum development to enhance physical education quality and student success.

In the Schools Division of Iloilo under the K to 12 Curriculum, the Physical Education program seeks to provide opportunities for the physical development of Filipino learners through the development of various competencies under the basic education curriculum by the provision of appropriate activities and programs in the instruction. Physical Education program aims to develop the physical prowess of the students, their agility, endurance, vitality, and kinesthetic skills, designed to help students to be mentally sound, physically strong, and emotionally balanced.

"Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013" (Republic Act No. 10533) and the 21st Century Philippine Education framework. Ensuring the quality of Physical Education Teacher Education (PETE) has been challenging due to an emerging paradigm of education in the Philippines, reshaped through the Policies, Standards, and Guidelines (PSG) of the program (Commission on Higher Education [CHED] Memorandum Order No. 80, series of 2017), has been designed to achieve Quality Physical Education (QPE) in the Philippines through producing highly competent and skilled physical educators (Dizon & Tolentino 2022).

The study investigates the interconnected roles of teachers' instructional competence, management support, and school infrastructure. This exploration is essential because each factor contributes uniquely to the educational environment and student outcomes. Teachers' instructional competence ensures effective delivery of curriculum and engagement, while management support fosters a conducive teaching and learning atmosphere through adequate resources and policy implementation. Concurrently, school infrastructure provides the necessary physical and technological environment conducive to learning. By examining these elements collectively, the study aims to identify how they synergistically influence academic achievement, providing insights that can inform policy and practice for enhancing educational quality and student success.

The examination of variables in the study among secondary school teachers has the potential to uncover significant relationships between instructional practices and competence strategies in physical education. Identifying which variables contribute most

significantly to the field of physical education can provide valuable insights for the Department of Education (DepEd). The researcher believes that this study will positively impact the teaching and learning process by highlighting key factors that enhance instructional competence. As an educator, the researcher is motivated to explore the roles of instructional competence, management support, and school infrastructure in teaching physical education among teachers in the Schools Division of Iloilo. This pursuit aims to inform and improve educational strategies, ultimately fostering a more effective physical education environment for both teachers and students.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to determine the teachers' instructional competence, management support and school infrastructure: bases for intervention program in the Schools Division of Iloilo, Philippines for School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of teachers' instructional competence as assessed by the respondents when taken as a whole and when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, length of service, and position?
2. What is the level of teachers' management support as assessed by the respondents when taken as a whole and when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, length of service, and position?
3. What are the school infrastructure as assessed by the respondents when taken as a whole and when classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, length of service, and position?
4. Are there significant differences in the level of teachers' instructional competence as assessed by the respondents and when they are classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, length of service, and position?
5. Are there significant differences in the level of teachers' management support as assessed by the respondents and when they are classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, length of service, and position?
6. Are there significant differences in the school infrastructure as assessed by the respondents and when they are classified according to age, sex, educational attainment, length of service, and position?
7. Are there significant relationships among teachers' instructional competence, management support and school infrastructure?
8. What innovation program may be developed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study was conducted to MAPEH teachers teaching physical education' on teachers' instructional competence, management support and school infrastructure in physical education in teaching physical education in the Schools' Division of Iloilo Philippines for school year 2023-2024.

The study used the descriptive-correlational methods of research with the aid of the questionnaire checklist. The survey method used since the researcher gathered data through the use of a questionnaire. Creswell and Guetterman (2019) defined a survey as a research method used for collecting data from a pre-defined group of respondents to gain information and insights on various topics of interest. On the other hand, correlational research is a type of non-experimental research method. A researcher measures two variables, understands and assesses the statistical relationship between them with no influence from any extraneous variable (Bhat, 2019). In this study, a correlational analysis was performed to determine the significant relationship between the teachers' instructional practices, competence and strategies in teaching physical education.

The independent variables are the personal factors of the respondents such as age, sex, educational attainment, length of service and position, and districts.

The dependent variables are teachers' instructional competence, management support and school infrastructure in physical education in teaching physical education.

Respondents

The respondents of the study consisted of the MAPEH teachers, teaching physical education in Schools Division, Province of Iloilo, Philippines for the School Year 2023-2024. Stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the study. The sample size were 375 teaching dance. In the First Congressional District, 75; Second Congressional District 67; in Third Congressional District 85, Fourth Congressional District the number of respondents were 76, and in the Fifth Congressional District, the number of respondents were 77, a total of 150 teachers, teaching physical education.

Instrument

The data gathering instruments use was a researcher-revised questionnaire to determine levels of instructional competence, management support and school infrastructure in physical education in teaching physical education. The researcher-revised questionnaire checklists for the learners consisted of three parts. Part I, respondents' profile that contained personal information which includes name (optional), age (40 years old and below, and 41years old and above), educational attainment (baccalaureate, masters and doctorate), length of service (20 years and below, and 21 years and above), position, (teacher I-III, and master teacher I-II), and district

(1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th).

Part II was the Instructional Competence questionnaire consisted of 15 items. Part III was a questionnaire about management support consisted of 15 items. Part IV will be a questionnaire about School Infrastructure consisted of 15 items.

The instrument used for gathering data on the instructional competence, management support, and school infrastructure in physical education was a researcher-made that was submitted for validation through the assistance of the research experts and statistician. To check whether the questions are appropriate, clear, reasonable, non-superficial, non-ephemeral, typical, and sufficiently inclusive, Good and Scates Criteria of Validation was employed. To finally make sure that the questionnaire is valid, suggestions and corrections from the validators was incorporated to produce the final copy. Panel validation was used to establish the validity of the questionnaire. Four panels who were experts in the subject matter being studied has selected to do the validation. Each question was analyzed whether the item was appropriate or needs revision. The comments, suggestions and recommendation of the panels was solicited, collated incorporated to the questionnaire.

The validated questionnaire was pilot tested with 25 MAPEH teachers who were teaching physical education in a school where the researcher has no affiliation. The objective of the pilot testing was to evaluate the questionnaire for irrelevant or unnecessary statements, confusing items and wording, respondent difficulties with the instructions, and issues with sequence and format, as well as to determine the average time required to complete it. The Cronbach's alpha results for the instrument indicated high reliability, with scores of 90.0 for instructional competence, 89.0 for management support, and 87.0 for school infrastructure, confirming the instrument's appropriateness for conducting the study in the context of physical education.

Procedure

Before the survey was conducted, the researcher sought the concurrence of the Dean of the Graduate School to administer the research instrument to the respondents. The researcher requests the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent and School Heads. Upon approval, the researcher went to the different schools in the Schools Division of Iloilo and administer the said questionnaire.

The researcher personally distributes the questionnaire through the assistance of the School Heads of the different schools in the Schools Division of Iloilo so that the purpose of the study was properly understood by the respondents to ensure the accuracy of the responses. Permission to participate in the study sought from each respondent. They informed that their privacy and confidentiality are going to be protected. They are assured that the information was solely for the research purposes.

For the safety of the of the respondents, in this regard, she used a two-way process in reaching out to her respondents by having an online and printed questionnaire. The researcher informs the school heads that open responses for the online questionnaire was counted only for one (1) week, the same with the retrieval of printed questionnaires from the teachers. When all the questionnaires will be accomplished, these was retrieved immediately.

When the administration of the questionnaire was done, the data was collated, encoded, tabulated and interpreted employing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) using appropriate statistical tools through the assistance of a statistician identified by Guimaras State University.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher secured the informed consent form from the respondents after informing them of the entirety of the research endeavor including the research objectives, procedure, the utility of the data collected, and securing that no harm is to be inflicted to the respondents. Only those who voluntarily signed the informed consent form were taken as respondents of this study.

Further, the results were presented based the independent variables and no names were unveiled to observe the confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analyzed data and its interpretation to determine the teachers' instructional competence, management support and school infrastructure in the Schools Division of Iloilo, Province of Iloilo, Philippines for the School Year 2023-2024.

Profile of Respondents in Terms of Age, Sex, Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Position

As to Age, there were 266 or 70.9 percent were 40 years and below, 108 or 28.8 percent were 41 years and above. As to sex, there were 174 or 46.4 percent were male and 200 or 53.5 percent were Female. As to educational attainment there were 284 or 75.7 percent were Bachelor's Degree holder, 77 or 20.5 percent were Master's Degree Holder and 14 or 3.7 percent were Doctorate Degree Holder. As to length of service, there were 268 or 72.5 percent were 15 years and below and 107 or 28.5 percent were 16 years and above. As to position, 346 or 92.3 percent were Teacher I-III and 29 or 7.7 percent were Master Teacher I-III.

The analysis of the respondent profile table reveals a diverse distribution across various demographic factors. The majority of respondents are aged 40 years and below, accounting for 70.9% of the sample, while 28.8% are 41 years and above. Female respondents slightly outnumber males, representing 53.3% of the total. Educational attainment is primarily at the Bachelor's level, with 75.7%

holding this degree, followed by 20.5% with a Master's degree and a minority of 3.7% with a Doctorate. In terms of length of service, the majority (71.5%) have served for 15 years or less, with 28.5% having 16 years and above. The majority of respondents (92.3%) hold positions as Teacher I-III, with a smaller percentage (7.7%) as Master Teacher I-III.

The respondent profile primarily comprises young, female teachers with Bachelor's degrees and less than 16 years of experience. The sample is distributed relatively evenly across congressional districts.

The Table 2 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of Age, Sex, Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Position.

Table 2. Profile of Respondents in Terms of Age, Sex, Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Position

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Age		
40 years and below	266	70.9
41 years and above	108	28.8
Sex		
Male	174	46.4
Female	200	53.5
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	284	75.7
Master's Degree	77	20.5
Doctorate Degree	14	3.7
Length of Service		
15 years and below	268	72.5
16 years and above	107	28.5
Position		
Teacher I-III	346	92.3
Master Teacher I-III	29	7.7
Total	375	100

Level of Teachers' Instructional Competence When Taken as a Whole and Classified into Age, Sex, Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Position

MAPEH teachers have "Very High" ($M=4.64$) level of instructional competence. Specifically, the results shows that the teachers teaching physical education have excellent competence in creatively developing guided learning materials in teaching physical education lessons ($M=5.00$); taking reflective action to improve the quality of learning ($M=4.97$); keeping abreast with recent developments in physical education ($M=4.89$); planning and coordinating educational development activities in teaching physical education to develop learners' creativity in physical education ($M=4.80$); making use of high technology equipment in teaching physical education to the benefit of educational development of learners' activities in order to better organize them ($M=4.80$); doing thorough adjustments of educational learning theory and principles in teaching physical education ($M=4.78$); establishing oneself as a trustworthy individual with a noble character who serves as a role, model for learners' and the wider community ($M=4.78$); linking with other schools for sharing best practices in physical education ($M=4.67$); upholding the objectives and goals of the MAPEH Curriculum for

Physical education as one of the required teaching competencies ($M=4.67$); demonstrating unique and artistic way of teaching physical education to learners ($M=4.67$); creating a unique technique relevant to the area of development that is being taught ($M=4.65$); performing learners' difficulty in physical education from teaching perspectives ($M=4.43$), and conducting assessment and evaluation of learning processes and outcomes in teaching physical education lessons ($M=4.34$).

Further, the data show that the respondents have "High" level of instructional competence or perceived to have good instructional abilities in acquiring a thorough understanding of the competency requirements and fundamental competencies of the subjects or development areas being taught ($M=4.04$) and utilizing the results of the assessment and evaluation for the benefit of learning and improvement of learners' learning in physical education ($M=4.11$).

These data highlight that the teachers who are teaching physical education are generally focusing on the instructional delivery and the things supplementing their teaching process and less prioritizing the curriculum itself and the by-product of instruction as essentials to augment the process of teaching.

Data were shown in Table 3.

Categorically, teachers who are teaching physical education were identified to have "Very High" instructional competence may they be 40 years old and below ($M=4.64$) or 41 years old and above ($M=4.65$); male ($M=4.67$) or female ($M=4.62$); Bachelor's degree ($M=4.31$) or Master's degree ($M=4.63$), either Doctorate degree ($M=4.65$) holders; with 15 years and below ($M=4.64$) or 16 years and above ($M=4.63$) years of teaching experience, and Teacher I-III ($M=4.55$) or Master Teacher I-III ($M=4.64$).

Table 3. *Level of Teachers' Instructional Competence When Taken as a Whole*

Items	Mean	D	Rank
Perform learners' difficulty in physical education from teaching perspectives	4.43	Very High	12
Do thorough adjustments of educational learning theory and principles in teaching physical education	4.78	Very High	6.5
Create a unique technique relevant to the area of development that is being taught	4.65	Very High	11
Plan and coordinate educational development activities in teaching physical education to develop learners' creativity in physical education	4.80	Very High	4.5
Make use of high technology equipment in teaching physical education to the benefit of educational development of learners' activities in order to better organize them	4.80	Very High	4.5
Conduct assessment and evaluation of learning processes and outcomes in teaching physical education lessons	4.34	Very High	13
Utilize the results of the assessments and evaluation for the benefit of learning and improvement of learners' learning in physical education	4.11	High	14
Demonstrate unique and artistic way of teaching physical education to learners	4.67	Very High	9
Establish oneself as a trustworthy individual with a noble character who serves as a role, model for learners' and the wider community	4.78	Very High	6.5
Take reflective action to improve the quality of learning	4.97	Very High	2
Develop creatively guided learning materials in teaching physical education lessons	5.00	Very High	1
Acquire a thorough understanding of the competency requirements and fundamental competencies of the subjects or development areas being taught	4.04	High	15
Keep abreast with recent developments in physical education	4.89	Very High	3
Link with other schools for sharing best practices in physical education	4.67	Very High	9
Uphold the objectives and goals of the MAPEH Curriculum for Physical education as one of the required teaching competencies	4.67	Very High	9
Overall	4.64	Very High	

Legend: Very High (VH) = 4.21-5.00; High (H) = 3.41-4.20; Moderate(M) = 2.61-3.40; Low(L)=1.81-2.60; Very Low (VL) = 1.00-1.80

The results are presented in Table 4.

The results simply imply that the respondents' demographic profile do not impact their level of instructional competence and demonstrated exceptionally high levels of instructional competence, as evidenced by their strong abilities in developing creative learning materials, engaging in reflective practices, and staying updated on the latest physical education trends.

Table 4. *Level of Teachers' Instructional Competence when Classified into Age, Sex, Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Position*

Variables	Mean	Description
As a Whole	4.64	Very High
<i>Age</i>		
40 Years Old and Below	4.64	Very High
41 Years Old and Above	4.65	Very High
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	4.67	Very High
Female	4.62	Very High
<i>Educational Attainment</i>		
Bachelor's Degree	4.31	Very High
Master's Degree	4.63	Very High
Doctorate Degree	4.65	Very High
<i>Length of Service</i>		
15 years and Below	4.64	Very High
16 year and Above	4.63	Very High
<i>Position</i>		
Teacher I-III	4.55	Very High
Master Teacher I-III	4.64	Very High

Legend: Very High (VH) = 4.21-5.00; High (H) = 3.41-4.20; Moderate(M) = 2.61-3.40; Low(L)=1.81-2.60; Very Low (VL) = 1.00-1.80

Despite of the very high level of instructional competence, the teachers who are Bachelor's degree is remarkably the lowest. This lead to the idea similar to Silvestre's (2021) that Graduate Education help equip the teachers by offering advance degree programs align with the need of teachers specifically in terms of teaching strategies, instructional materials, mastery of content knowledge and assessment in various specializations in MAPEH.

Level of Management Support as Assessed by the Teachers Teaching Physical Education When Taken as a Whole and Classified in Terms of Age, Sex, Educational Attainment, Length in Service and Position

Table 5 presented the data.

Table 5. *Level of Management Support as Assessed by the Teachers Teaching Physical Education When Taken as a Whole*

Items	Mean	Description
The administration supports the development of teachers in teaching physical education through seminars and trainings	4.40	Very High
There are adequate resources (e.g., dance studio space, equipment) to support effective teaching in physical education	4.87	Very High
The management actively promotes professional development opportunities for MAPEH teachers by enhancing workshops to support teaching in physical education	4.67	Very High
The school head is responsive to feedback from physical education teachers regarding curriculum and teaching methods	4.66	Very High
There is clear communication from management about expectations and goals for the physical education program	4.92	Very High
The management actively seeks input from physical education teachers when making decisions impacting the physical education lessons	4.82	Very High
There is timely and constructive feedback to physical education teachers to enhance their teaching performance	4.86	Very High
Management encourages innovation in physical education methods	4.87	Very High
The management values diversity and inclusion in the physical education program	4.46	Very High
The management ensures a safe and supportive environment for both physical education teachers and learners	4.73	Very High
The management provides adequate training and support for the use of technology in physical education instructions	4.82	Very High
The management demonstrates a commitment to the well-being and work-life balance of physical education teachers	4.50	Very High
The management communicates effectively about changes in policies or procedures related to physical education programs	4.84	Very High
The management provides opportunities for physical education teachers to engage with the broader community	4.39	Very High
The management recognizes and acknowledges the achievements and contributions of physical education teachers	4.45	Very High
Overall	4.68	Very High

Legend: Very High (VH) = 4.21-5.00; High (H) = 3.41-4.20; Moderate(M) = 2.61-3.40; Low(L)=1.81-2.60; Very Low (VL) = 1.00-1.80

When taken as a whole, the teachers teaching physical education identified the management support to be "Very High" with mean of 4.68. Teachers were very supportive when providing clear communication there clear communication from management about expectations and goals for the physical education program (M=4.92); management encourages innovation in physical education methods (M=4.87); when there are adequate resources (e.g., dance studio space, equipment) to support effective teaching in physical education (M=4.87); when there is timely and constructive feedback to physical education teachers to enhance their teaching performance (M=4.86); when the management communicates effectively about changes in policies or procedures related to physical education programs (M=4.84); when the management actively seeks input from physical education teachers when making decisions impacting the physical education lessons (M=4.82); when the management provides adequate training and support for the use of technology in physical education instructions (M=4.82); when the management ensures a safe and supportive environment for both physical education teachers and learners (M=4.73); when the management actively promotes professional development opportunities for MAPEH teachers by enhancing workshops to support teaching in physical education (M=4.67); when the school head is responsive to feedback from physical education teachers regarding curriculum and teaching methods (M=4.66); when the management

demonstrates a commitment to the well-being and work-life balance of physical education teachers (M=4.50); when the management values diversity and inclusion in the physical education program (M=4.46); when the management recognizes and acknowledges the achievements and contributions of physical education teachers (M=4.45); when the administration supports the development of teachers in teaching physical education through seminars and trainings (M=4.40), and when the management provides opportunities for physical education teachers to engage with the broader community (M=4.39).

Clear communication of expectations and goals, as well as adequate resource allocation, emerged as critical factors influencing program success. Conversely, areas requiring improvement include fostering community engagement and providing robust teacher development opportunities.

When the demographic profile of the respondents were considered, the results revealed that the teachers teaching physical education have “Very High” level of management support. Whether the teachers are 40 years old and below (M=4.69) or 41 years old and above (M=4.67); male (M=4.67) or female (M=4.67); Bachelor’s degree (M=4.61) or Master’s degree (M=4.73) either Doctorate degree (M=4.63) holders; with 15 years and below (M=4.60) or 16 years and above (M=4.66) in the service, and Teacher I-III (M=4.62) or Master Teacher I-III (M=4.64), they were very supportive of information, descriptions, or skills in teaching dance.

The results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. *Level of Management Support as Assessed by the Teachers Teaching Physical Education When Classified in Terms of Age, Sex, Educational Attainment, Length in Service and Position*

Variables	Mean	Description
As a Whole	4.68	Very High
<i>Age</i>		
40 Years Old and Below	4.69	Very High
41 Years Old and Above	4.67	Very High
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	4.67	Very High
Female	4.70	Very High
<i>Educational Attainment</i>		
Bachelor’s Degree	4.61	Very High
Master’s Degree	4.73	Very High
Doctorate Degree	4.63	Very High
<i>Length of Service</i>		
15 years and Below	4.60	Very High
16 years and Above	4.66	Very High
<i>Position</i>		
Teacher I-III	4.62	Very High
Master Teacher I-III	4.64	Very High

Legend: Very High (VH) = 4.21-5.00; High (H) = 3.41-4.20; Moderate(M) = 2.61-3.40; Low(L)=1.81-2.60; Very Low (VL) = 1.00-1.80

These findings underscore the overall positive management climate while highlighting the need for nuanced support strategies to address specific gender-related needs. Teachers with less experience prioritize a supportive environment, while those with more experience emphasize innovation encouragement. These further underscore the importance of consistent, yet adaptable, management support to meet the evolving needs of teachers at different career stages. Furthermore, tailored management support to meet the specific needs of different teacher roles is perceived to be important in the effective teaching of dance.

Level of School Infrastructure When Taken as a Whole and Classified into Age, Sex, Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Position

Descriptive analysis of school infrastructure reveals a strong emphasis on physical environment. When taken as a whole, the respondents declared that they have “Very High” level of school infrastructure with a total mean of 4.60 which means that they demonstrated excellent in utilizing schools’ facilities in physical education. The respondents further specified that their school provides a ventilated classroom to ensure learners comfortable environment while performing activities in physical education classes (M=4.92); advocates for investment in infrastructure that directly contribute to enhance learners’ physical education performance (M=4.89); promotes a culture of physical fitness and encourages learners to engage in regular physical education activities (M=4.83); provides the ambiance of physical education facilities, which is conducive to a positive and focused learning experience (M=4.83); has grounds that are properly maintained and safe for physical education activities (M=4.82); provides adequate supervision and support during physical education classes and extracurricular sports activities (M=4.63); ensures good facilities in physical education conducive in fostering a positive and engaging educational experience (M=4.63); offers a diverse range of sports equipment to cater different interests and activities of the learners in physical education (M=4.55); provides changing rooms and locker facilities adequately accommodate students participating in physical education classes (M=4.37); allocates sufficient budget and resources on maintaining and upgrading physical education facilities (M=4.31); collaborates with external organizations or clubs to enhance learners’ exposure to different sports and physical education activities (M=4.30); provides accessible facilities for learners with disabilities to participate in physical

education activities (M=4.30), and has well-equipped sports equipment (M=4.21) which were labeled as “Very High”. Moreover, the respondents generally declared that their school highlight the importance of infrastructure to facilitate physical education a well manage classroom environment and provide adequate audio equipment, available for playing music for physical education classes, both were labeled as “High” with a mean of (M=4.20).

Descriptive analysis shows that school infrastructure highlights a strong emphasis on well-ventilated classrooms for student comfort during physical education and infrastructure investment to enhance physical education performance. Conversely, the analysis reveals a lower prioritization of audio equipment for physical education classes and the role of infrastructure in classroom management.

This indicates a clear recognition of physical infrastructure's importance in supporting academic performance, yet reveals varying priorities among educators regarding specific infrastructural needs.

The data is shown in Table 7.

Table 7. *Level of School Infrastructure When Taken as a Whole*

Items	Mean	Description
There are well-equipped sports equipment	4.21	Very High
Advocate for investment in infrastructure that directly contribute to enhance learners' physical education performance	4.89	Very High
Ensures good facilities in physical education conducive in fostering a positive and engaging educational experience	4.63	Very High
Highlight the importance of infrastructure to facilitate physical education a well manage classroom environment	4.20	High
provide adequate audio equipment, available for playing music for physical education classes	4.20	High
Provides a ventilated classroom to ensure learners comfortable environment while performing activities in physical education classes	4.92	Very High
Offers a diverse range of sports equipment to cater different interests and activities of the learners in physical education	4.55	Very High
Provide changing rooms and locker facilities adequately accommodate students participating in physical education classes	4.37	Very High
Grounds are properly maintained and safe for physical education activities	4.82	Very High
Promotes a culture of physical fitness and encourages learners to engage in regular physical education activities	4.83	Very High
Provides adequate supervision and support during physical education classes and extracurricular sports activities	4.63	Very High
Provides accessible facilities for learners with disabilities to participate in physical education activities	4.30	Very High
Allocates sufficient budget and resources on maintaining and upgrading physical education facilities	4.31	Very High
Collaborates with external organizations or clubs to enhance learners' exposure to different sports and physical education activities	4.30	Very High
Provides the ambiance of physical education facilities, which is conducive to a positive and focused learning experience	4.83	Very High
Overall	4.60	Very High

Legend: Very High (VH) = 4.21-5.00; High (H) = 3.41-4.20; Moderate(M) = 2.61-3.40; Low(L)=1.81-2.60; Very Low (VL) = 1.00-1.80

The results show that there is a “Very High” level of school infrastructure assessed by the respondents regardless of their age (40 years and below, M=4.53; 41 years and above, M=4.52), sex (male, M=4.53; Female, M=4.60), educational attainment (Bachelor’s Degree, M=4.53; Master’s Degree, M=4.56; Doctorate Degree (M=4.57), length of service (15 years and Below, M=4.53; 16 years and Above, M=4.56), and position (Teacher I-III, M=4.53; Master Teacher I-III, M=4.54).

These findings highlight the general importance of school infrastructure for academic performance while suggesting the need for age-specific considerations to optimize its impact. Also, it was revealed that the shared belief in infrastructure's importance while underscoring the need for gender-specific support to optimize its impact on student outcomes. In addition, the results underscore the widespread belief in infrastructure's importance for academic success, with specific priorities varying slightly based on educational attainment. While the respondents express high satisfaction, their specific priorities slightly diverge, reflecting the nuances of their experiences. Further, shared belief in the critical role of school infrastructure for optimal learning, with specific preferences emerging

based on teaching experience and responsibilities is evident.

Data were shown in Table 8.

Table 8.

Variables	Mean	Description
As a Whole	4.60	Very High
<i>Age</i>		
40 Years Old and Below	4.53	Very High
41 Years Old and Above	4.52	Very High
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	4.53	Very High
Female	4.60	Very High
<i>Educational Attainment</i>		
Bachelor's Degree	4.53	Very High
Master's Degree	4.56	Very High
Doctorate Degree	4.57	Very High
<i>Length of Service</i>		
15 years and Below	4.53	Very High
16 years and Above	4.56	Very High
<i>Position</i>		
Teacher I-III	4.53	Very High
Master Teacher I-III	4.54	Very High

Legend: Very High (VH) = 4.21-5.00; High (H) = 3.41-4.20; Moderate(M) = 2.61-3.40; Low(L)=1.81-2.60; Very Low (VL) = 1.00-1.80

Differences in Teachers' Instructional Competence when Classified According to Age, Sex, Length of Service and Position

No significant difference was found in perceived instructional competence between teachers from 40 years old and below, and 41 years old and above. Mean between two variables exhibited, (4.6363) compared to 41 years old and above (4.6475). A t-test analysis yielded a non-significant T-value of -.635 and a corresponding p-value of 0.526, well above the alpha level of 0.05. These results support the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in instructional competence between 40 years old and below, and 41 years old and above.

Table 9. Teachers' Instructional Competence when Classified According to Age, Sex Length of Service and Position

Variables	Mean	Df	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Age					
40 years and below	4.6363				
41 years and above	4.6475	372	-.635	0.526	Not Significant
Sex					
Male	4.6667				
Female	4.6173	372	3.117	0.002	Significant
Length of Service					
15 years and below	4.6440				
16 years and above	4.6299	373	.424	0.800	Not Significant
Position					
Teacher I-III	4.6401				
Master Teacher I-III	4.6391	373	.033	0.973	Not Significant

A significant difference in perceived instructional competence was found between male and female teachers. Male teachers exhibited a higher mean instructional competence score (4.6667) compared to female teachers (4.6173). The t-test yielded a significant t-value of 3.117 and a corresponding p-value of 0.002, which is less than the alpha level of 0.05. This evidence supports the rejection of the null hypothesis, indicating that there is a statistically significant difference in instructional competence between male and female teachers.

No significant difference was found in perceived instructional competence between teachers with 15 years or less of service and those with 16 or more years of service. The mean ratings for the two groups were very similar (4.6440 and 4.6299, respectively). A t-test yielded a non-significant t-value of 0.424 and a p-value of 0.800, far exceeding the alpha level of 0.05. These results support the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in perceptions of instructional competence based on length of service.

No significant difference was found in perceived instructional competence between Teacher I-III and Master Teacher I-III positions. Despite a negligible mean difference in ratings (4.6401 for Teacher I-III and 4.6391 for Master Teacher I-III), the t-test yielded a non-significant t-value of 0.033 and a p-value of 0.973, far exceeding the alpha level of 0.05. These findings support the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in instructional competence perceptions based on teacher position.

The analysis explored the relationship between teachers' instructional competence and various demographic factors. The findings indicated that there were no significant differences in instructional competence based on teacher age, length of service, or position. However, a significant difference was observed with respect to gender, where male teachers demonstrated notably higher mean instructional competence scores compared to their female counterparts. This suggests that gender may play a role in influencing instructional competence, underscoring the need to consider demographic factors when assessing teacher competence. These results highlight the importance of incorporating a nuanced understanding of how demographic variables impact instructional effectiveness, which can inform targeted professional development and support strategies.

Differences in Teachers' Instructional Competence when Classified According to Educational Attainment and District

No significant difference was found in teachers' instructional competence based on educational attainment (Bachelor's, Master's, or Doctorate degrees). An ANOVA analysis yielded a non-significant F-value of 0.271 and a corresponding p-value of 0.762, well above the alpha level of 0.05. These results indicate no substantial variation in instructional competence among teachers with different educational qualifications. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is supported.

No significant difference was found in perceived instructional competence across the five districts. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) yielded a negligible F-value of 0.005 and a p-value of .102, far exceeding the alpha level of 0.05. These results indicate no substantial variation in instructional competence perceptions among teachers from the different districts. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in instructional competence based on district is strongly supported. The analysis of teachers' instructional competence across different educational attainment levels and districts revealed no significant differences. ANOVA results showed non-significant F-values and corresponding p-values greater than the alpha level for both educational attainment and district. These findings indicate that teachers' instructional competence was consistent regardless of their educational qualifications or the district in which they taught. Consequently, the null hypotheses of no significant differences were accepted for both variables.

Data were shown in Table 10.

Table 10. *Differences in Teachers' Instructional Competence when Classified According to Educational Attainment and District*

Sources of Variations	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F _{value}	p-value	Remarks
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT						
Between Groups	2	.013	.006			
Within Groups	372	8.894	.024	.271	.762	
Not Significant						
Total	374	8.907				
DISTRICT						
Between Groups	4	0.001	.000			
Within Groups	370	8.906	.024	.005	.102	
Not Significant						
Total	374	8.907				

Differences in Management Support when Classified According to Age, Sex, Length of Service and Position

No significant difference was found in perceived management support between teachers aged 40 and below and those aged 41 and above. The mean ratings for the two groups were quite similar (4.6228 for the younger group and 4.6062 for the older group). A t-test yielded a non-significant t-value of .644 and a p-value of 0.520, well above the alpha level of 0.05. These results support the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in perceptions of management support based on age.

There was no significant difference in perceived management support between male and female respondents. The mean ratings for males (4.6050) and females (4.6287) were very similar. A t-test yielded a non-significant t-value of -1.009 and a p-value of 0.313, well above the alpha level of 0.05. These results support the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in perceptions of management support based on gender.

No significant difference was found in perceived management support between teachers with 15 years or less of service and those with 16 or more years of service. The mean ratings for the two groups were 4.6035 and 4.6536, respectively. A t-test yielded a t-value of -1.945 and a p-value of 0.053, which is marginally above the typical alpha level of 0.05. While this result approaches statistical significance, it does not provide sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in perceptions of management support based on length of service.

No significant difference was found in perceived management support between Teacher I-III and Master Teacher I-III positions. Despite a slight mean difference in ratings (4.6160 for Teacher I-III and 4.6391 for Master Teacher I-III), the t-test yielded a non-significant t-value of -.528 and a p-value of 0.598, exceeding the alpha level of 0.05. These findings support the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in management support perceptions based on teacher position.

The analysis examined the influence of management support on learners' academic performance across various demographic groups. Results indicated no significant differences in academic performance based on age, length of service, or position. Consistent non-

significant t-values and p-values greater than 0.05 across these categories suggest a uniform experience of management support's impact on academic performance among these groups. Similarly, no significant gender-based differences were found in relation to management support and academic performance. Consequently, the null hypotheses of no significant differences were accepted for all demographic categories examined. These findings suggest a consistent level of management support across the studied demographic groups, indicating a uniform impact on learners' academic performance regardless of age, sex, length of service, or position.

Data were shown in Table 11.

Table 11. *Management Support when Classified According to Age, Sex, Length of Service and Position*

Variables	Mean	Df	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Age					
40 years and below	4.6228				
41 years and above	4.6062	372	.644	0.520	Not Significant
Sex					
Male	4.6050				
Female	4.6287	372	-1.009	0.313	Not Significant
Length of Service					
15 years and below	4.6035				
16 years and above	4.6536	373	-1.945	0.053	Not Significant
Position					
Teacher I-III	4.6160				
Master Teacher I-III	4.6391	373	-.528	0.598	Not Significant

Differences in Management Support when Classified According to Educational Attainment and District

No significant difference in perceived management support was found among teachers with varying levels of educational attainment (Bachelor's, Master's, and Doctorate degrees). An ANOVA revealed a non-significant F-value of 1.815 and a p-value of 0.164, exceeding the alpha level of 0.05. These findings indicate no substantial variation in management support perceptions based on teacher education. Consequently, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in management support by educational attainment is accepted. No significant difference was found in perceived management support across the five districts. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) yielded a non-significant F-value of 0.005 and a p-value of 0.437, well above the alpha level of 0.05. These results indicate no substantial variation in management support perceptions among teachers from the different districts. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in management support based on district is accepted.

The analysis investigated the differences in management support across varying levels of teacher education and school districts. ANOVA results revealed no significant differences in academic performance attributable to these factors, as indicated by non-significant F-values and p-values exceeding the 0.05 threshold for both educational attainment and district. These findings led to the acceptance of the null hypotheses, confirming no significant differences in management support across these demographic groups. This suggests that management support is consistently experienced regardless of teachers' qualifications or geographic location. The implications of these results point to the potential influence of factors beyond individual teacher characteristics, such as school-level administrative practices or the overarching organizational culture, which may play a more pivotal role in shaping the management support perceived by educators. This insight highlights the importance of focusing on broader systemic factors when addressing management support in educational settings.

Table 12. *Differences in Management Support when Classified According to Educational Attainment and District*

Sources of Variations	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F _{value}	p-value	Remarks
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT						
Between Groups	2	.185	.092			
Within Groups	372	18.932	.051	1.815	.164	Not Significant
Total	374	19.117				
DISTRICT						
Between Groups	4	.090	.022			
Within Groups	370	19.027	.051	.005	.437	Not Significant
Total	374	19.117				

Differences in School Infrastructure when Classified According to Educational Attainment and District

No significant difference was found in perceived school infrastructure among teachers with different levels of educational attainment (Bachelor's, Master's, and Doctorate degrees). An ANOVA revealed a non-significant F-value of 0.942 and a p-value of 0.391, exceeding the alpha level of 0.05. These findings indicate no substantial variation in school infrastructure perceptions based on teacher education. Consequently, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in school infrastructure by educational attainment is accepted.

No significant difference was found in perceived school infrastructure across the five districts. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) yielded a non-significant F-value of 0.060 and a p-value of 0.993, well above the alpha level of 0.05. These results indicate no

substantial variation in school infrastructure perceptions among teachers from the different districts. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in school infrastructure based on district is accepted.

The analysis examined the differences of school infrastructure across varying levels of teacher education and school districts. Results from ANOVA indicated no significant differences in academic performance attributable to these factors. Non-significant F-values and p-values greater than 0.05 for both educational attainment and district suggest a consistent experience of school infrastructure's impact on academic performance across these groups. Consequently, the null hypotheses of no significant differences were accepted. These findings imply that factors beyond teacher qualifications or geographic location, such as overall funding allocation or maintenance policies, may exert a more substantial influence on school infrastructure and subsequent student outcomes.

Table 13. *Differences in School Infrastructure when Classified According to Educational Attainment and District*

Sources of Variations	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F _{value}	sig. (2-tailed)	Remarks
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT						
Between Groups	2	.025	.012			
Within Groups	372	4.925	.013	0.942	.391	Not Significant
Total	374	4.950				
DISTRICT						
Between Groups	4	.003	.001			
Within Groups	370	4.947	.013	.060	.993	Not Significant
Total	374	4.950				

Differences in School Infrastructure when Classified According to Age, Sex, Length of Service and Position

No significant difference was found in perceived school infrastructure between teachers aged 40 and below and those aged 41 and above. The mean ratings for the two groups were quite similar (4.5288 for the younger group and 4.5204 for the older group). A t-test yielded a non-significant t-value of .643 and a p-value of 0.521, well above the alpha level of 0.05. These results support the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in perceptions of school infrastructure based on age.

Data were shown in Table 14.

Table 14. *School Infrastructure when Classified According to Age, Sex, Length of Service and Position*

Variables	Mean	Df	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Age					
40 years and below	4.5288				
41 years and above	4.5204	372	.643	0.521	Not Significant
Sex					
Male	4.5249				
Female	4.5277	372	-.231	0.817	Not Significant
Length of Service					
15 years and below	4.5261				
16 years and above	4.5265	373	-.027	0.978	Not Significant
Position					
Teacher I-III	4.5249				
Master Teacher I-III	4.5425	373	-.794	0.428	Not Significant

There was no significant difference in perceived school infrastructure between male and female respondents. The mean ratings for males (4.5249) and females (4.5277) were very similar. A t-test yielded a non-significant t-value of -.231 and a p-value of 0.817, well above the alpha level of 0.05. These results support the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in perceptions of school infrastructure based on gender.

No significant difference was found in perceived school infrastructure between teachers with 15 years or less of service and those with 16 or more years of service. The mean ratings for both groups were nearly identical (4.5261 and 4.5265, respectively). A t-test yielded a negligible t-value of -.027 and a p-value of 0.978, well above the alpha level of 0.05. These results support the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in perceptions of school infrastructure based on length of service.

The analysis revealed no significant difference in perceived school infrastructure between Teacher I-III and Master Teacher I-III positions. Despite a slight mean difference in ratings (4.5249 for Teacher I-III and 4.5425 for Master Teacher I-III), the t-test yielded a non-significant t-value of -.794 and a p-value of 0.428, exceeding the alpha level of 0.05. These findings support the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in school infrastructure perceptions based on teacher position.

The analysis examined the variation in school infrastructure across diverse demographic groups. The results showed no significant differences in academic performance related to school infrastructure when classified by age, length of service, or position, as indicated by consistent non-significant t-values and p-values exceeding 0.05 across these categories. Furthermore, no significant gender-based differences were observed, reinforcing the uniformity of school infrastructure's influence among all groups. Consequently, the null

hypotheses of no significant differences were accepted across all examined demographic categories. These findings suggest that the impact of school infrastructure is consistently experienced across various demographic groups, highlighting that factors other than demographic characteristics may play a more critical role in influencing perceptions or effectiveness of school infrastructure in supporting academic performance. This consistency underscores the need for a broader focus on improving school infrastructure as a universal factor benefiting all educators and students, regardless of demographic distinctions.

Relationship between the Instructional Competence, Management Support, and School Infrastructure

To determine the relationship between teachers' instructional competence, management support, and school infrastructure, the researcher employed Pearson r.

The analysis revealed a significant relationship between instructional competence, management support, with a Spearman rho value of 0.288 and a p-value of 0.000. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 significance level, this indicates a significant, albeit low, correlation. The findings suggest that higher levels of instructional competence are associated with higher levels of management support. Thus, the null hypothesis, which posited no significant relationship between teachers' instructional competence, management support, was rejected.

Results revealed a significant relationship between management support, and school infrastructure, with a Spearman rho value of 0.043 and a p-value of 0.000. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 significance level, this indicates a strong and significant correlation. The findings suggest that higher levels of management support are associated with higher levels of and school infrastructure. Thus, the null hypothesis, which posited no significant relationship between management support, and school infrastructure, among respondents, was rejected.

Results revealed a significant relationship between teachers' instructional competence, and school infrastructure, with a Spearman rho value of 0.153 and a p-value of 0.003. Since the p-value is less than the 0.05 significance level, this indicates a strong and significant correlation. The findings suggest that higher levels of instructional competence, are associated with higher levels of school infrastructure. Thus, the null hypothesis, which posited no significant relationship between instructional competence, and school infrastructure, among respondents, was rejected.

The study's findings underscore the important and interconnected relationships between instructional competence, management support, and school infrastructure within the educational environment. Well-developed infrastructure appears to be a key driver in enhancing instructional practices, thereby improving teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes. Furthermore, strong management support is crucial for the development and upkeep of quality infrastructure, which directly benefits instructional activities. The link between instructional competence and management support highlights the essential role of leadership in fostering an environment that promotes instructional excellence. These insights suggest that targeted improvements in one area, such as enhancing school infrastructure, can positively impact both instructional competence and management support, ultimately leading to comprehensive advancements in the overall educational setting.

Table 15. *Relationship between the Teachers' Instructional Competence, Management Support, and School Infrastructure*

		Instructional Competence	Management Support	School Infrastructure
INSTRUCTIONAL Competence	Pearson Correlation	1	-.298**	-.153**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.003
	N	375	375	375
MANAGEMENT Support	Pearson Correlation	-.298**	1	-.043
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.405
	N	375	375	375
SCHOOL Infrastructure	Pearson Correlation	-.153**	-.043	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.405	
	N	375	375	375

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Intervention Program in Teaching Physical Education Goals

The intervention program aims to enhance teacher competence, management support, and school infrastructure specific to teaching Physical Education (PE) in accordance with DepEd's directives for delivering high-quality physical education. The primary goal is to develop teachers' skills and confidence in delivering engaging and effective PE lessons, supported by proactive management and adequate facilities. This program seeks to foster a holistic learning environment that not only improves students' physical skills and fitness but also promotes overall well-being and lifelong healthy habits.

Additionally, the program aims to foster a supportive management culture that recognizes the importance of PE and actively works to provide the necessary resources, scheduling, and policy backing to support its effective delivery. Upgrading school infrastructure is also a key goal, with the aim of providing safe, well-equipped, and accessible spaces that facilitate a variety of physical activities.

Ultimately, the program seeks to create a learning environment where PE is integral to students' physical, social, and emotional development, promoting lifelong fitness and healthy habits.

Objectives

The objectives of the intervention program are to: (1) improve PE teachers' instructional competence by providing targeted professional development, including workshops on innovative teaching strategies, classroom management, and assessment in physical education; (2) strengthen management support by training school leaders to effectively prioritize and integrate PE within the overall school curriculum, ensuring that resources and scheduling align with program goals; and (3) enhance school infrastructure by upgrading sports facilities, providing necessary equipment, and ensuring safe and accessible spaces for physical activities. These objectives aim to create a comprehensive support system that enhances the delivery of PE, making it an integral and valued part of the school experience.

The program also seeks to establish clear performance indicators for PE teachers and school management, promoting accountability and continuous improvement. By integrating these objectives, the program aims to create a sustainable model of PE instruction that can be replicated across different schools and districts, aligning with DepEd's goal of providing high-quality education that supports the holistic development of every learner.

Rationale

The rationale for this intervention program is based on the recognition of Physical Education as a critical component of the overall educational curriculum, as highlighted by DepEd's commitment to holistic student development. PE not only contributes to physical fitness but also teaches essential life skills such as teamwork, discipline, and resilience. However, effective PE instruction requires competent teachers, supportive management, and appropriate infrastructure. By addressing these areas, the program aims to mitigate current challenges such as limited resources, inadequate training, and lack of support, thereby enhancing the overall quality of PE teaching. This intervention aligns with DepEd's goal of nurturing well-rounded learners who are equipped with the skills and attitudes necessary for a healthy lifestyle.

This program is grounded in the belief that competent teachers, supportive management, and quality infrastructure are interdependent factors that collectively enhance the educational experience. By investing in teacher competence, the program seeks to empower educators with the skills needed to engage students and foster a love for physical activity. Strengthening management support ensures that these efforts are sustained and valued within the broader school context, while improved infrastructure provides the necessary physical spaces for diverse and inclusive PE activities. This holistic approach aligns with DepEd's mission to deliver inclusive, equitable, and quality education, preparing students not just academically, but for healthy and active lives beyond the classroom.

On Instructional Competence

Instructional competence among teachers is adapting to the evolving demands of physical education by utilizing creative teaching methods and continuous professional development. The importance of ongoing training and reflective practices in maintaining high teaching standards regardless of the teacher's age.

While both genders demonstrated strong abilities in developing creative learning materials, engaging in reflective practices, and staying updated on the latest physical education trends, male teachers competence in understanding subject competency requirements and utilizing assessment results for improved student learning is promising.

Further, instructional competence may gradually improves as educational attainment increases as teachers proficiently craft engaging learning materials, implement reflective practices, and stay knowledgeable about the field. Strong commitment to instructional excellence in physical education would imply attaining higher level of learning.

Instructional competence in physical education may be improved regardless of the length of service of the teachers. Physical Education teachers demonstrated exceptional ability in crafting engaging learning materials, implementing reflective practices, and staying updated on educational trends. The dedication to professional growth and excellence in teaching displayed by educators at all career stages is a reflection of the number of years in handling the subject.

Teacher position constitutes both a responsibility that reflects competency in creating engaging learning materials, staying current with educational developments, and fostering student creativity through development activities. While strong in subject matter knowledge, their utilization of assessment data for improvement is remarkably noticeable. The teachers with higher teaching position consistently demonstrated exceptional ability in developing innovative materials, implementing reflective practices, and staying informed about educational trends. Their assessment utilization skills, though strong, were slightly lower than their other competencies.

Furthermore, schools in various districts demonstrated strong proficiency in developing creative learning materials and engaging in reflective practice. Additionally, all districts displayed a solid understanding of core competencies - a district-wide commitment to instructional excellence.

On Management Support

Management support for physical education programs highlights key areas of strength and weakness. Clear communication of

expectations and goals, as well as adequate resource allocation, emerged as critical factors influencing program success. Conversely, areas requiring improvement include fostering community engagement and providing robust teacher development opportunities.

Regardless of the age and sex, Physical Education teachers express strong satisfaction with management, particularly in areas of clear communication, resource provision, and goal setting. Male teachers emphasize innovation and resource adequacy, while female teachers prioritize communication, feedback, and creating a supportive environment. Positive management climate needs for nuanced support strategies to address specific age- and gender-related needs.

The educational attainment and lengths of service of Physical Education teachers strengthens express strong satisfaction with management support. Core areas of strength include clear communication, resource adequacy, and timely feedback. While both groups value these elements, nuances exist. Teachers with less experience prioritize a supportive environment, while those with more experience emphasize innovation encouragement. Consistent, yet adaptable, management support will meet the evolving needs of teachers at different career stages.

In addition, importance of tailored management support to meet the specific needs of different teacher roles is evident in all districts. While there is a general consensus on strong management support, specific priorities vary. A robust, district-wide commitment to supporting physical education programs, with tailored approaches to address specific local needs is a necessity in the current curricular landscape.

On School Infrastructure

Teaching Physical Education subjects would require well-ventilated classrooms for student comfort as an investment to enhance physical education performance. A lower prioritization of audio equipment for physical education classes and the role of infrastructure in classroom management specifically affect the expected learning outcomes. This indicates a clear recognition of physical infrastructure's importance in supporting academic performance, yet reveals varying priorities among educators regarding specific infrastructural needs.

Perception to school infrastructure of Physical Education teachers may have subtle difference in emphasis when age is taken into consideration. Younger teachers prioritize ventilated classrooms, infrastructure investment, and a physical fitness culture. Older teachers share these priorities but also emphasize creating a conducive learning environment and providing well-equipped sports equipment. Thus, general importance of school infrastructure for academic performance is evident, while suggesting the need for age-specific considerations to optimize its impact.

School infrastructure as a determinant of academic performance has a consistently high perception among both male and female teachers. While both genders express strong satisfaction, their priorities differ slightly. Male teachers prioritize ventilated classrooms, infrastructure investment, and safe grounds. Female teachers share these priorities but additionally emphasize fostering a physical fitness culture and maintaining a well-managed classroom environment. The shared belief in infrastructure's importance while underscoring the need for gender-specific support to optimize its impact on student outcomes is taken into account.

Physical Education teachers have consistently high perceptions of school infrastructure. Bachelor's degree holders prioritize ventilated classrooms, infrastructure investment, grounds maintenance, and a physical fitness culture. Master's degree holders emphasize similar factors, with an added focus on accessibility for students with disabilities. Doctorate degree holders prioritize physical fitness culture, conducive learning environments, and investment advocacy. These imply that the widespread belief in infrastructure's importance for academic success, with specific priorities varying slightly based on educational attainment matters.

Similarly, teachers with fewer than 15 years perceived ventilated classrooms, infrastructure investment, and fostering a physical fitness culture and rating sports equipment as equally important with the other support factors. Those with 16 or more years emphasize accessible facilities for students with disabilities, in addition to ventilated classrooms and a physical fitness culture. While both groups express high satisfaction, their specific priorities slightly diverge, reflecting the nuances of their experiences.

Physical Education teachers considered overall school infrastructure as highly important. This belief might be a reflection of their teaching position. This shared belief in the critical role of school infrastructure for optimal learning, with specific preferences is based on teaching experience and responsibilities.

All districts perceived school infrastructure would prioritize well-ventilated classrooms, safe grounds, and investment advocacy, with a particular focus on sports equipment.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the findings underscore the critical importance of accounting for demographic factors when interpreting research results and designing effective interventions. Tailoring strategies to the specific needs of diverse educators and learners is essential for maximizing outcomes and promoting equity in education.

Teachers' Instructional Competence provides critical insights into the strengths and areas for growth among physical education teachers. Teachers excel in developing creative learning experiences and employing reflective practices, demonstrating a commitment to

continuous improvement. However, opportunities exist to enhance subject matter expertise and the utilization of assessment data to inform instruction. To optimize student outcomes, targeted professional development should address these areas, elevating overall teacher effectiveness in physical education.

The descriptive analysis illuminates the critical role of management support in shaping the success of physical education programs. Clear communication of program expectations and adequate resource allocation emerged as foundational elements for effective instruction. However, opportunities for enhancing teacher-community engagement and providing robust teacher development were identified. To optimize student outcomes, management should prioritize strategies to foster these areas, ultimately elevating the overall effectiveness of physical education programs.

The study underscores the pivotal role of physical infrastructure in shaping student achievement. A strong emphasis on well-ventilated classrooms and physical education facilities highlights the correlation between conducive learning environments and academic success. While the importance of audio equipment and classroom management is acknowledged, these areas warrant increased attention. Despite varying priorities, educators unanimously recognize the critical impact of infrastructure on student learning. To optimize outcomes, a holistic approach addressing all infrastructural needs is imperative.

The study's findings underscore the important and interconnected relationships between instructional competence, management support, and school infrastructure within the educational environment. Well-developed infrastructure appears to be a key driver in enhancing instructional practices, thereby improving teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes.

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